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Co- and Ni- free oxygen electrode performance improvement by electrode/electrolyte interface tuning

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Abstract

One of the present challenges for Solid Oxide Cells (SOC) developers is to produce durable and high performance cell units for high temperature electrolysis applications, utilizing cost efficient raw materials with low recycling costs to reach a large scale industrialization. Nickel and cobalt, which are state-of-the-art compounds in the manufacturing of SOC electrodes, bring critical concerns regarding the need of high conditioning and recycling costs related to their carcinogenic properties. In addition, cobalt is recognized since 2017 as Critical Raw Materials (CRM) for the EU community, due to the high economical risk associated to its supply within Europe (55% of the world's cobalt being sourced from Central Africa). Use of Co- and Ni- free electrode materials would provide a significant reduction of use of CRM in European SOC manufacturing, and offers SOC cell and stack manufacturers the benefit of a more environmental-friendly and lower cost manufacturing process and the potential of using recycled materials from previous manufacturing.

To this end, TNO has undertaken to develop a novel Co- and Ni-free oxygen electrode design based on the (La,Ca,Sr)FeO₃ perovskite class of materials. However the removal of nickel and cobalt in the oxygen electrode tends to increase the overpotential of the electrode. Taking into account this last drawback, TNO aims to optimize the performance of this new Co- and Ni-free compounds by microstructural improvement in terms of particle size, porosity and surface roughness. In addition, a novel electrode architecture is proposed by creating a patterned electrode/electrolyte interface, thus enhancing the triple phase boundary density between electrolyte and oxygen electrode. This novel concept is envisaged to improve the electrode performance and to prevent electrode delamination during SOC operations. A higher triple phase boundary density contributes to lower the local partial oxygen pressure between electrolyte and oxygen electrode, known as critical degradation phenomena of the oxygen electrode at high current density under electrolysis conditions.

The latest development of the novel Co- and Ni- free oxygen electrode design developed at TNO, within the FCHJU NewSOC project will be presented during the conference.

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1. Introduction

The realization of a cost competitive integration of Solid Oxide Electrolyzer (SOE) in industrial scale applications demands a decrease in stack cost [1]. The reduction in stack cost can be realized by bringing down manufacturing process costs and decreasing the use of both high cost raw materials and/or critical raw material (CRM). Nickel and cobalt, state-of-the-art compounds in the Solid Oxide Cell (SOC) manufacturing, require high conditioning and recycling costs related to their carcinogenic properties. In addition, cobalt is considered as CRM by the EU community since 2017 [2], due to the high economical risk associated to its supply within Europe (55% of the world's cobalt being sourced from Central Africa). Though the amount of cobalt required within the SOE technology is limited (approximately <0.04 w% in stack), it is especially the huge demand for cobalt in other applications, like batteries for electrical vehicles [3], that makes the supply of cobalt critical. The research presented in this paper aims at reducing the use of cobalt and nickel in the SOC manufacturing, by exploring low cost Co- and Ni-free oxygen electrode materials, aiming towards competitive performance and lifetime for SOE applications.

A-site substituted perovskite-type lanthanum ferrites (La,Ca,Sr)FeO₃ have been reported frequently to be of interest as oxygen electrode for Solid Oxide Cells [4-26]. The main reported benefits of this class of material are a better match of coefficients of thermal expansion with zirconia-based electrolyte [4, 10, 19, 22, 24, 26] and relatively low reactivity with zirconia [6,8,12,16,19,21]. The claimed low reactivity of (La,Sr)FeO₃ (LSF) and (La,Ca)FeO₃ (LCF) materials with the zirconia electrolyte potentially enables the direct deposition on the electrolyte without the need for a ceria barrier layer [8,21]. This is in contrast with the state-of-the-art Co- and Ni-containing materials, where a ceria barrier layer is required in order to prevent chemical interaction between oxygen electrode and zirconia electrolyte.

This paper presents the first step in the development towards high performance and robust lanthanum ferrite based oxygen electrodes. The comparison in reactivity and electrochemical performance between lanthanum ferrites deposited directly on the zirconia electrolyte or in combination with a ceria barrier layer forms the subject of this study.

2. Scientific Approach

The performance of three compositions of lanthanum ferrite oxygen electrodes have been examined with respect to electrode microstructure, chemical compatibility with the electrolyte and electrochemical performance. Table 1 shows the materials being used in this study. LSCF is being used as reference Co-containing oxygen electrode material. CGO20 was selected as porous interfacial layer for this study. TZ3Y, commonly used as high strength electrolyte material in electrolyte supported cells, is the electrolyte material of choice.

Table 1. Compositions of the different cell components

Oxygen electrode	(La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4}) _{0.99} Co _{0.2} Fe _{0.8} O _{3-δ} (LSCF) La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} FeO _{3-δ} (LSF82) La _{0.8} Ca _{0.2} FeO _{3-δ} (LCF82) La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4} FeO _{3-δ} (LSF64)
Barrier layer	Ce _{0.8} Gd _{0.2} O _{2-δ} (CGO20)
Electrolyte	97%mol ZrO ₂ -3%mol Y ₂ O ₃ (TZ3Y)

Symmetrical cells have been selected as cell configuration in order to get information on the electrochemical performance at zero current by means of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). The ohmic resistance indicates the degree of electrode coverage on the electrolyte surface, the presence of spreading resistance and/or presence of poor conducting interface reaction products. The polarization resistance gives a good indication of the electrocatalytic activity of the different electrode compositions. The microstructure and presence of chemical interaction between the layers will be examined by SEM and EDX analysis of the fracture surface of the symmetrical cells.

3. Experiments

3.1 Preparation of the symmetrical cell

Commercial powders were used for the preparation of the symmetrical cells. The yttria-doped zirconia at 3%mol (TZ3Y) was provided from Tosoh. The gadolinium doped ceria $\text{Ce}_{0.8}\text{Gd}_{0.2}\text{O}_{2-\delta}$ (CGO20) and the air electrode materials $(\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4})_{0.99}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (LSCF), $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ (LSF64), $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ (LSF82) and $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ (LCF82) were supplied from Cerpotech. The oxygen electrode materials were manufactured with similar particle size distribution with a $D_{50} = 0.9\text{-}1.2 \mu\text{m}$. TZ3Y electrolyte supports, with $90 \pm 1 \mu\text{m}$ thickness of diameter of $20.09 \pm 0.03 \text{ mm}$, were produced by tape casting process of organic based slurries prepared with the commercial TZ3Y powder from Tosoh, and sintered at 1400°C for 1h. Subsequently, CGO20 and air electrode materials pastes were prepared on organic based recipe for deposit by screen-printing process. One layer of CGO20 was applied on both side of the electrolyte supports, with a diameter of 19.5 mm, and sintered to the temperature of 1300°C for 1h. Oxygen electrodes (LSCF, LSF82, LCF82 and LSF64) were subsequently produced two printed layers and sintered at 1100°C for 1h. Table 2 summarizes the different configurations of symmetrical cells prepared.

Table 2. Symmetrical cells configurations

Air electrode	TZ3Y electrolyte without barrier layer	TZ3Y electrolyte with porous CGO20 barrier layer
LSCF	A1	A2
LSF82	B1	B2
LCF82	C1	C2
LSF64	D1	D2

3.2 Materials morphology and composition characterization

Microstructural and elementary characterization of the symmetrical cells were performed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), back-scattering electrons microscopy (BSE) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) with a Hitachi SU70 equipment with Oxford Aztec 3.1 hard and software for EDX analysis. The microstructural characterization by SEM and BSE of the oxygen electrode surfaces and cross section of the symmetrical cells were conducted with 5kV. Compositional analysis made by EDX were performed at 15kV. Prior to EDX analysis the samples were coated with a 6nm thin Pt-Pd conductive layer for optimized EDX analysis. The analyses results are corrected for this layer. Thickness and porosity measurements were performed by image analysis with the ImageJ 1.52a software [27].

3.3 Electrochemical characterization

The electrochemical characterization of the symmetrical cells was performed by impedance (EIS) measurements with a ProboStat (Norecs) equipment, by conventional four-point DC technique. Gold grids of 100 mesh with thickness of 0.4 mm and a diameter of 20mm were

used. EIS measurements were conducted with an Ivium Vertex potentiostat, at open-circuit voltage (OCV) within a frequency range from 1MHz to 0.1Hz and an amplitude of 10mV, between 900 and 550°C. Measurement were performed under air conditions with a flow of 100ml/min. EIS spectra fitting was performed with the ZView software with two time constant equivalent circuit for high frequencies and low frequencies as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Equivalent circuit used for EIS spectra fitting

4. Results

4.1 Microstructure characterization and reactivity

An overview of the microstructural and compositional characterization of the symmetrical cells manufactured without (TZ3Y-air electrode) and with a ceria barrier layer (TZ3Y-CGO20-air electrode) are respectively presented in Table 1 and Table 2. In addition, Table 3 presents the layer thicknesses of the electrolyte, porous ceria layer and oxygen electrode obtained from the SEM imaging of the symmetrical cells prepared with barrier layer.

Table 1: Microstructural and compositional characterization of interface electrolyte-oxygen electrode for the symmetrical cells manufactured without ceria barrier layer (TZ3Y-air electrode)

		— Zr Wt% — Y Wt% — La Wt% — Fe Wt% — Sr Wt% — Ca Wt% — Co Wt%
Sample	Cross section imaging	Elementary analysis
A1		
B1		
C1		
D1		

Table 2: Microstructural and compositional characterization of interface electrolyte-oxygen electrode for the symmetrical cells manufactured with a ceria barrier layer (TZ3Y-CGO20-air electrode)

Table 3: Electrolyte, barrier layer and oxygen electrode layer thicknesses measured from SEM imaging analysis for the symmetrical cells manufactured with CGO20 barrier layer

Sample	TZ3Y electrolyte	CGO20 barrier layer	Air oxygen electrode
LSCF (A2)	89.0 ± 0.3 μm	1.37 ± 0.1 μm	19.3 ± 0.2 μm
LSF82 (B2)	88.5 ± 0.3 μm	2.30 ± 0.07 μm	21.3 ± 0.1 μm
LCF82 (C2)	90.5 ± 0.3 μm	2.63 ± 0.05 μm	10.4 ± 0.1 μm
LSF64 (D2)	89.7 ± 0.3 μm	1.64 ± 0.08 μm	8.5 ± 0.2 μm

Microstructural characterization

The microstructural characterization of the symmetrical cells prepared without ceria layer (Table 1) shows an overall good adhesion of the oxygen electrode at the surface of the electrolyte. For the symmetrical cells prepared with ceria layer (Table 2), similar observations can be made for the LSF64 and LSCF compositions, while weaker adhesion is found at CGO20 layer-electrolyte interface for LSF82 and LCF82. For all samples, the ceria barrier layer presents a porous microstructure, but layer thickness variations are observed between the samples (Table 3). A thinner ceria barrier layer (1.4-1.6 μm) is observed for the LSF64 and LSCF compositions compared the ones observed for LSF82 and LCF82 (2.3-2.6 μm). The different oxygen electrodes (Table 3) show variations in layer thickness between 8 and

20 μm . In addition, slight difference of grains coalescence and porosity can be remarked in Table 1 and Table 2, between the different oxygen electrode compositions. The symmetrical cells being manufactured with the same paste manufacturing protocol, screen-printing process (2 layers deposition) and sintering process (1100°C/1h for oxygen), an effect of the initial oxygen electrode material composition on the microstructure is certainly assumed. In later work, optimization of the screen-printing process (adjustment of layer deposition number) and sintering temperature program are required to achieve optimized electrode microstructure (porosity, grains coalescence, layer thickness) for each electrode composition.

Compositional characterization

The compositional characterization of the electrode-electrolyte interface of the symmetrical cells manufactured without ceria barrier layer (Table 1), shows formation of interdiffusion products for every sample. For the Sr-containing electrodes (LSCF, LSF82 and LSF64), a Sr migration is observed at the interface with a doubling of Sr weight percentage compared to the air electrode composition, and Zr diffusion is found over 1-3 μm within the electrode as previously seen in the study of Simner *et al.* [6]. For LSCF and LSF82, this observation is in agreement with the literature where the reactivity between LSCF and YSZ is known above a temperature of 1000°C [13], and above 950°C between YSZ and LSF82 [s]. The formation of SrZrO_3 and $\text{La}_2\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_7$ for each composition are assumed to occur respectively at the interface and within the oxygen electrode as seen in literature [5,11], but further compositional investigation are currently conducted as other interdiffusion products (e.g. $\text{Sr}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$) are also mentioned in literature [6]. For LCF82, no Zr incorporation is observed in the electrode layer as previously observed by Anderson *et al.* [6], but unlike claimed in literature with use of 8YSZ, Ca and Fe migration takes place at the TZ3Y-LCF82 interface with 3 to 4 times higher concentration of Ca for a sintering temperature of 1100°C. Additional compositional characterization of the interdiffusion product is currently under investigation.

For the TZ3Y-CG20-air electrode symmetrical cell samples (Table 2), the presence of the CGO20 barrier layer although not dense, reduces and in the case of LSF82 completely prevents the formation of interdiffusion products after sintering. For LSCF and LSF64, a Sr/Zr reactivity is still visible spread from the electrolyte interface-CGO20 and within the barrier layer. But, the barrier layer seems preventing Zr migration in the electrode. No Zr migration can be observed for LSCF and lower Zr %wt in the LSF64 electrode. In the case of LCF82, the presence of Ca is still observable at electrolyte-CGO20 interface, but Fe migration seems prevented at the electrolyte interface.

The outcome of the microstructural and compositional characterization performed in this work can be summarized as followed:

- Both LSF and LCF oxygen electrode compositions applied directly on top of zirconia shows electrode good adhesion properties, but a significant amount of interface reaction products takes place at the sintering temperature of 1100°C.
- In presence of the current quality porous CGO20 layer, only LSF82 shows no detectable interface reaction products after sintering at 1100°C.
- Weaker CGO-electrolyte interface while thicker CGO 20 layer takes place for LSF82 and LCF82 having no or low reactivity compared to LSF64 and LSCF. An improvement of CGO-electrolyte interface adhesion will be therefore required in future work.

4.2 Electrochemical characterization

The EIS measurements conducted in this work give insight on the impact of the use of a ceria barrier layer with A-site substituted perovskite-type lanthanum ferrites (La,Ca,Sr) FeO_3 and assess the electrochemical performance of each Co-free oxygen electrode materials at different operating temperatures in comparison with the state-of-the-art SOC oxygen electrode material LSCF.

Impact of presence of ceria barrier layer

Figure 2 illustrates an example of the difference of electrochemical performance of A-site substituted perovskite-type lanthanum ferrites (La,Ca,Sr)FeO₃ with or without use of a 20GCO barrier layer and Table 4 gives the overview of the ohmic and polarization resistances obtained at OCV and 700°C for each oxygen electrode with and without ceria layer.

Figure 2: -Nyquist-plot at OCV at 700°C for the symmetrical cells manufactured with LSF82 without and with CGO20 barrier layer (respectively sample B1 and B2)

Table 4: Ohmic and polarization resistance in ohm.cm² at 700°C and OCV for LSF82, LCF82, LSF64 and LSCF with and without ceria layer

Air Electrode composition	Without 20GCO-layer (sample series X1)		With 20GCO-layer (sample series X2)	
	R _{ohm}	R _{pol}	R _{ohm}	R _{pol}
LSCF	2.18	1521.7	1.78	0.78
LSF82	2.81	126.1	2.35	0.31
LCF82	2.37	2001.4	2.34	0.73
LSF64	2.29	247.8	2.62	0.31

The presence of the 20GCO barrier layer results in a significant reduction of the polarization resistance for all A-site doped lanthanum ferrites, as observed for LSCF. Apart from LSF64 composition, the ohmic resistance for the samples with the 20GCO layer has slightly reduced resistance values, indicating that the ceria barrier layer diminishes reactions taking place at the electrode-electrolyte interface.

Electrochemical performance of lanthanum ferrite samples with GCO-barrier layer

Figure 3a and Figure 3b respectively present the ohmic and polarization resistance values as function of operating temperature (550-900°C), for the lanthanum ferrite oxygen electrodes manufactured on symmetrical cells with a CGO20 barrier layer.

Figure 3: a) Ohmic and b) polarization resistance values as function of temperature for the lanthanum ferrite oxygen electrodes in presence of CGO20 barrier layer

For the ohmic contribution (Figure 3a), the following observations can be made:

- LCF and LSF oxygen electrode compositions have an overall higher ohmic resistance compared to LSCF over the all temperature range studied (550-900°C)
- The highest ohmic resistance is observed for LSF64 composition
- Similar T-dependence behavior of the ohmic resistance is observed between as LSF64, LCF82 and LSCF, while LSF82 presents a different T-dependency with lower increase of the ohmic resistance as function of temperature.

For the polarization contribution (Figure 3a), the following observations can be made:

- The LSF compositions have lower polarization resistance than LSCF over the all temperature range studied (550-900°C)
- LCF has lower polarization resistance than LSCF at high temperature (700-900°C)
- At low T-range the 82 compositions have similar T-dependency, the 64 compositions have also similar T-dependency but at different slope

As general outcome of the electrochemical characterization conducted on the lanthanum ferrite oxygen electrodes manufactured on symmetrical cells, LCF and LSF compositions have slightly higher ohmic resistance than LSCF. In presence of a CGO20 barrier layer, the polarization resistance is significantly improved for every oxygen electrode composition. LSF compositions show lower polarization resistances compared to LSCF on all operating temperature of SOC cells (550-900°C), while LCF82 only presents acceptable performance compared to LSCF for operating temperature above 700°C.

4.3 Discussion

In absence of ceria barrier layer, interface reaction products (Zr/Sr for LSF compositions and Ca/Fe/Zr for LCF82) very likely result in the observed slight increase in ohmic resistance and significant increase in polarization resistance. The reactivity observation is not completely in line with literature [6,8,12,16,19,21], showing relatively low reactivity for lanthanum ferrite materials and zirconia at the sintering temperature of 1100°C. A possible explanation is the sensitivity of reactivity to sintering temperature and exact starting composition or morphology of the starting powders.

The general outcome of the present work is that lanthanum ferrite samples perform better in presence of a ceria layer, confirming the outcome of some researches in literature [6]. In addition of promoting significantly the ionic conductivity at the electrolyte-oxygen electrode interface evidenced by a significant reduction of the polarization resistance, the ceria layer also promotes lower or no reactivity at the electrolyte-electrode interface (Table 2). Apparently the ceria layer, despite its observed porosity, has the potential to diminish the reactivity between the oxygen electrode and the zirconia electrolyte compounds. A correlation between observed ohmic resistance and reactivity is not clearly established. A similar temperature dependence behavior of the ohmic resistance is observed for LSF64, LCF82 and LSCF (Figure 3a), for which interdiffusion products are observed at the electrolyte-CGO interface (Table 2), while LSF82 showing no reactivity have a different T-dependency with lower increase of the ohmic resistance as function of temperature. However, LSCF showing the highest level of Sr/Zr reactivity at the ceria-zirconia interface still has the lowest ohmic resistance. The difference in ohmic resistance observed is probably also related to the differences in electronic conducting behavior for the different electrode compositions (Table 5) and rather low layer thickness values for several of the different electrodes (Table 3). A clear correlation between observed polarization resistance and reactivity cannot be given. It is remarkable that the LSF82 without observed reactivity performs at the low polarization

resistance comparable to LSF64, which has reaction products at the interface. LSCF with high Sr-segregation show higher polarization resistance in line with expectation.

Table 5: Electronic conductivity ($\sigma_{el.}$) values of the selected (La,Ca,Sr)FeO₃ and LSCF

Material	Composition	$\sigma_{el.}$ (S/cm)	ref
LSCF	La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4} Co _{0.2} Fe _{0.8} O _{3-δ}	325 (600°C)	[28]
		87 (800°C)	[4]
LSF82	La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} FeO _{3-δ}	57 (800°C)	[12]
		80 (460°C)	
LSF64	La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4} FeO _{3-δ}	283 (800°C)	[13]
		128 (800°C)	[4]
LCF82	La _{0.8} Ca _{0.2} FeO _{3-δ}	110 (700°C)	[22]

4. Conclusions

In the present work, the performance of three compositions of lanthanum ferrite oxygen electrodes (LSF82, LCF82 and LSF64) has been examined in the development towards high performance and robust Co-free oxygen electrodes for SOFC and electrolyzers applications. Electrode microstructure, chemical compatibility with the electrolyte and electrochemical performance were characterized on symmetrical cells without and with a porous ceria layer and compared with the performance of LSCF, currently used as state-of-the-art oxygen electrode material in the Solid Oxide Cell manufacturing. The comparison in reactivity and electrochemical performance between lanthanum ferrites deposited directly on the zirconia electrolyte or in combination with a ceria barrier layer permitted to give the following conclusions:

- a/ A ceria barrier layer is needed for lanthanum ferrite materials, especially when the oxygen electrode is manufactured at sintering temperature of 1100°C, to reduce interdiffusion products formation and improve the ionic conductivity at the electrolyte-electrode interface.
- b/ Using LSF82 does not require a fully dense ceria barrier layer in order to prevent reactivity at sintering temperature of 1100°C. It makes LSF82 a promising material to replace LSCF as high performance and robust Co-free oxygen electrodes.

In future work, further improvement of lanthanum ferrites electrodes is required with respect to ohmic resistance by varying electrode thickness, sintering temperature. In addition, polarization resistance can be further reduced by enhanced triple phase boundary density by microstructure engineering and using a patterned interface. Single cell implementation of the lanthanum ferrites will contribute to validate their performance under SOFC and electrolyzer conditions.

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